

CASE STUDY**WALMART- INDIA VS. CHINA****RAJNI KAMBOJ**

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ABSTRACT

Wal-Mart is the world's largest retailer and grocery chain by sales. Wal-Mart is so large that its 2010 sales were almost 50% more than its 5 closest competitors combined, including Target (TGT) and Sears Holdings (SHLD). Wal-Mart earned \$408 billion in revenue in FY2010, a 1% increase from 2009¹. The company operates 8,416 stores worldwide; with over 4,000 of them in international markets. Wal-Mart stores earned 51% of their revenue from grocery sales in 2010, with sales of entertainment, electronics, and toys a distant second at 13% of Wal-Mart stores' revenue. The company plans to open 145-160 new stores in 2011. All around the world, Wal-Mart operated 2747 Supercenters, 803 discount stores, & 150 neighborhood format stores at the end of 2010. According to CEO Mike Duke; the company is planning to create 500,000 jobs worldwide by 2015².

This case study gives insight into Wal-Mart, a major global retailer's possible entry into the Asian countries especially in India & China. It describes the strategy followed by Wal-Mart in India & China & its contribution in the economy of these two developing countries. The case also throws a light on the hurdles faced by Wal-Mart in India & China also.

Key words: *Discount stores, TGT, SHLD, Super centers, Wal-Mart*

¹<http://walmartstores.com/>

²[WMT2010GlobalSustainabilityreport](#)

NOTHING LIKE WALMART

The top 15 retailers in the world are Wal-Mart (US), Carrefour(France), Royal Ahold (Netherlands), Home Depot(US), Kroger(US), Metro AG(Germany), Target(US), Ibertson's(US), Kmart(US), Sears Holdings(US), Safeway(UK), Costco(US), Tesco(UK), JC Penney(US), Aldi Einkauf (Germany) & Wal-Mart is one of the biggest retail players in the world. Wal-Mart is so much bigger than any retailer that it's not easy to compare.

In the US it became famous over time for its "everyday low prices" (EDLP) concept. Efficient supply chain management is at the core of its business. But when they expanded over time to countries like China and India, they realized the fact that it. Wal-Mart had to struggle in Asia's developing markets to maintain its corporate philosophy of 'every day low prices' Due to Wal-Mart's low prices, consumers gravitate to Wal-Mart stores during economic downturns. As a result, the company's comparable store sales increased by 3.5% during the worst toughest year (2009-10).

Wal-Mart has 8,500 stores in 15 countries, under 55 different names. Internationally, the company operates in Argentina, Brazil, Canada, Chile, China, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, India, Japan, Mexico, Nicaragua, Puerto Rico and the UK. The company operates under its own name in the United States, including the 50 states. It also operates under its own name in Puerto Rico. It operates in Mexico as Walmex, in the United Kingdom as Asda, in Japan as Seiyu, and in India as Price. It employs around 2.1 million people around the world.

In 2010, the company's US comparable store sales fell by 0.8%-Wal-Mart operates 8,500 stores across three business segments of retail stores worldwide that offer a wide array of general merchandise including groceries, apparel, electronics, and small appliances. Over 54% of the company's stores are located in the United States, with the majority of international stores located in Central and South America and China. The company focuses on offering the lowest prices across its business segments, which together earned \$408 billion in revenue in 2010, a 1% increase from sales in 2009. Wal-Mart's largest business segment is its namesake Wal-Mart stores, which accounted for 63.8% of the company's revenue in 2010. On April 15, 2010, "Fortune" magazine announced Wal-Mart replaces Exxon Mobil is once again the Fortune top 500 of the United States.

LITERATURE REVIEW

David Neumark, Junfu Zhang & Stephen Ciccarella: (The effect of Wal-Mart on local labour market): David estimate the effects of Wal-Mart stores on county-level employment and earnings, accounting for endogeneity of the location and timing of Wal-Mart openings that most likely biases the evidence against finding adverse effects of Wal-Mart stores. There is stronger evidence that total payrolls per person decline, by nearly five percent in the aggregate, implying that residents of local labor markets earn less following the opening of Wal-Mart stores. And in the South, where Wal-Mart stores are most prevalent and have been open the longest, the evidence indicates that Wal-Mart reduces retail employment, total employment, and total payrolls per person.

Times of India (Is Wal-Mart retailing in India?):

Those keeping a close watch on the operations of Best Price Modern Wholesale — the brand under which Bharti Wal-Mart stores are being run — say that "the JV is carrying out retail business in the garb of wholesale". It's not as if it is always the fault of the retailer — sometimes even enthusiastic consumers find a way to beat the system to get that bargain.

Terry. Harrison: A supply chain is a network of facilities and distribution options that perform the functions of procurement of materials, transformation of materials into intermediate and finished products and the distribution of the finished products to customers. Supply chain finds its place in both services as well and manufacturing industry. Supply chain can also be explained as the association of the retailers, distributors, transporters and suppliers who come together and share the process of sale, delivery and production of a particular product or service

Dealbook (Wal-Mart to Invest in Chinese Online Retailer): China has the largest number of Internet users, about 420 million, according to the latest government survey. As a start-up, 360buy.com has grown along with online commerce in China. Analysts say e-commerce is growing at an explosive pace in China, with many shoppers ordering goods online and having them delivered instantly, and cheaply, sometimes by local services that use bicycles. Su Huiyan, an analyst at i-Research, a Shanghai-based firm that tracks Web developments, said online commerce in China is growing very fast above to expectations.

OBJECTIVE OF CASE STUDY

This case study focused on the following objectives:

1. To determine promotional strategies adopted by Wal-Mart in India & China.
2. Hurdles faced by Wal-Mart in India & China
3. SWOT analysis of Wal-Mart
4. Is Wal-Mart more successful in China as compare to India?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study aims to determine the strategies adopted by Wal-Mart to grow in India & China. For this purpose secondary data has been collected from various sites, magazine & newspapers.

WALMART UNITS (AS ON 31st JANUARY, 2010)³

Total global units: 8416

Suppliers – More than 100, 000 worldwide

Customers – Millions around the world

Associates – More than 2 million worldwide

Wal-Mart worldwide net sale: \$405 billion

Wal-Mart U.S net sale: \$258.2 billion

Sam's club: \$46.7 billion

Wal-Mart international net sale: \$100.1 billion

Total Revenue (FY 2010): \$408,214 million (0.9% increase over 2009)

Operating profit of Wal-Mart (FY 2010): \$23,950 million (5.1% increase over 2009)

Net profit (FY2010): \$14,335 million (7% increases over 2009)

INTERNATIONAL DATA SHEET – MARCH 2010⁴

Market	Retail units	Date of entry
Mexico	1472	November 1991
Canada	317	November 1994
Brazil	436	May 1995
Argentina	44	August 1995
China	283	July 1999
United Kingdom	371	March 2002
Japan	371	September 2005
Costa Rica	170	September 2005
<i>El Salvador</i>	<i>77</i>	<i>September 2005</i>
Guatemala	164	September 2005
Honduras	55	September 2005
Nicaragua	55	September 2005
Chile	253	January 2009
India	1	May 2009

WAL MART IN INDIA

The Indian retail industry is the fifth largest in the world. The Indian retail market accounted for \$ 200 billions. The industry is growing at a pace of 25-30% annually. According to the 8th Annual Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) of AT

Kearney, India retail industry is the most promising emerging market for investment. In 2007, the retail trade in India had a share of 8-10% in the GDP of the country. In 2009, it rose to 12% and 22% at the end of 2010.

In last few years, the consumer spending in India climbed up to 75%. As a result, it is expected to go up to US\$ 833 billion by the year 2013. By the year 2013, the organized sector is also expected to grow at a CAGR of 40%. It is further expected to reach US\$ 1.3 trillion by the year 2018 at a CAGR of 10%.

India is the 11th country, where Wal-Mart entered its retail chains. The reason for Wal-Mart's entry in India is clear –The Indian middle class. The world's biggest retailer had been silently working on its strategy for India for around two years. Mom-and-pop stores and traditional distribution networks dominated the \$375 billion Indian retail market. Wal-Mart Inc. believed that by the year 2015, 35% of India's retail sales could be from chain stores.

WAL MART RETAIL UNITS IN INDIA (AS ON 31st MARCH 2011)⁵

- Total retail units: 05
- Associates: 1665
- Best Price: 1

KEY COMPETITORS OF WAL MART IN INDIA

- Future groups Retail Venture
- Big Bazaar
- Food Bazaar
- Pantaloons
- RelianceFresh
- Aditya Birla Group-More

- Tata's retail venture: star India Bazar

³WMT2010GlobalSustainabilityreport

⁴<http://www.scribd.com/doc/36206320/Supply-Chain-Management-of-Walmart>

WHY WAL MART ENTERED IN INDIA

1. Economic Growth: Increase in GDP of India.
2. Market Size: The size of India's retail trade is estimated at \$200 billion and growing at twenty five to thirty per cent annually,
3. Increasing Purchasing power of Indians:
4. Indians are price sensitive & Wal-Mart can earn a lot by its 'Every day low price strategies'.
5. Increasing Young population - spending power
6. Rapid Urbanization
7. Growing middle-class population
8. Brand Consciousness
9. Consumerism
10. Growing advertising and promotional activities results into growth in Consumption patterns.
11. Availability of Cheaper raw material and trims.

JOINT VENTURE BETWEEN WAL MART & BHARTI ENTERPRISES

As foreign corporations are not allowed to directly enter the retail sector in India, So Wal-Mart entered through a joint venture with Bharti group in India. Bharti is one of India's leading business groups with interests in telecom, agri-business, insurance and retail, and Wal-Mart is the world's leading retailer, renowned for its efficiency and expertise in logistics, supply chain management and sourcing. Under the agreement, Bharti and Wal-Mart hold a 50:50 stake in Bharti Wal-Mart Private Limited. The Bharti manage the front end

involving opening of retail outlets, while Wal-Mart will take care of the back end, such as cold chains and logistics & handle the Wholesale.

Bharti Retail has also entered into a technical collaboration with Wal-Mart whereby Wal-Mart provides critical technical support to Bharti Retail. Since April 2008, Bharti Retail has opened 117 Supermarket format stores in the states of Punjab, Haryana, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Madhya Pradesh and Delhi and ten (10) Compact Hyper format store in the states of Punjab, Haryana, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh and Delhi.

⁵India_Fact_Sheet.2010

The first wholesale cash-and-carry facility named "Best Price Modern Wholesale" opened in Amritsar in May 2009, a second in Zirakpur (Near Chandigarh), a third in Jalandhar, a fourth in Kota and a fifth in Bhopal. The JV in India expects to open 10 to 12 Best Price Modern Wholesale stores and employ approximately 8,000 – 9,000 people by March 2012.

WALMART STRATEGIES IN INDIA

1. To give ordinary folk the chance to buy the same thing as rich people.
2. Selling branded products at low cost
3. Non dependence on any single vendor
4. Reliability on its own distribution system

OPPORTUNITIES FOR INDIA

1. Modernization of Retail Industry.
2. World-class shopping experience.
3. International standards.
4. Employment to millions of Indians.

5. Elimination of middle-men and agents, thus protecting Indian.
6. Farmers from exploitation: According to a study by the Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER), larger retail chains pay a 25% higher price for produce compared to what the farmers get generally from the market. And farmers selling to the retailers directly earn 60% higher profits.

BARRIERS FOR WAL MART IN INDIA

Political factors

1. Organizations may create a monopoly in the market.
2. Left leaning parties and communist parties opposing because it may kill unorganized retail sector.
3. The country's 15-million" mom -and-pop" outlets out of business

Legal factors

1. Under India's tight foreign investment rules, no overseas chains are permitted in the retail sector
2. Flexible labor laws
3. Reforms in the urban land ceiling and tenancy laws etc

Social factors

1. Language and Cultural factors is a barrier to globalization.
2. Distribution of income
3. Consumerism and changes in Indian Culture
4. Change in Lifestyle

Technological Factors

1. New discoveries and innovations like software for retail houses.

2. Speed of technology transfer - inventory management Use of Internet and E-commerce
3. Increasing Online shopping

WAL MART'S FUTURE IN INDIA

South Asia is still dominated by mom-and-pop grocery stores, but—as in the US about 70 years ago—the supermarket sector is expanding and will eventually overtake family-run shops, the economist gleans from a new study. "Many people assume that Asia's shopping habits are peculiar to the region and uniquely resistant to change," the authors write—but sheer demand will change all that.

India's small stores have survived so far with the the help of the government. They pay a lower rate of tax and adhere to a less stringent standard of hygiene. But if the tiny stores want to endure, notes the economist, they may have to organize in a serious way. Far- fetched? May be not. As the Indian study points out, even Wal-Mart founder Sam Walton himself started out operating a tiny five-and-dime.

WILL WAL MART SUCCEED IN INDIA?

It will succeed because

1. It has the best know how to provide the right set products to the right set of customers.
2. Customers are also hungry for new ways of shopping.
3. Wal-Mart Company has tremendous sourcing efficiencies which will bring economies of scale from day one.

WAL MART IN CHINA

Wal-Mart began its retail operations in China in 1996, with the opening of a supercenter and Sam's Club in Shenzhen. Wal-Mart's Global Procurement Office opened in February 2002. In February 2007, Wal-Mart purchased a 35 percent interest in Trust-Mart. Wal-Mart has around 40 outlets and 34 supercentres in China. Wal-Mart purchases billions worth of merchandise directly from China every year. If Wal-Mart were a country, its imports are so substantial that it would be China's sixth largest export country.

Over 54% of the company's stores are located in the United States, with the majority of international stores located in Central and South America and China. In 2002 and 2003, Wal-Mart was elected as one of the "Most Respected Companies in China" by the Enterprise Management Case Study Center of Beijing University and the Economic Observer. Wal-Mart operating in 19 cities, including Shenzhen, Dongguan, Kunming, Dalian, Shantou, Fuzhou, Shenyang, Xiamen, Harbin, Changchun, Changsha, Nanchang, Beijing, Jinan, Qingdao, Nanjing, Tianjin, Nanning and Guiyang . In 2006 Wal-Mart imported 27 billion of Chinese products. Wal-Mart imports are responsible for 11% of the growth of the total US trade deficit with China between 2001 & 2006.⁶

China is the largest & the fastest growing on line retailer. Wal-Mart invested a huge amount in China's 360 buy.com. In 2010, Wal-Mart, along with five other companies, invested around \$500 million into 360buy.com. Wal-Mart depends heavily on China for manufacturing its merchandise as it purchases billions of dollars worth of merchandise every year. Additionally, many of the company's suppliers like Mattel (MAT) manufacture their products in China, which in turn are sold in Wal-Mart stores. By outsourcing

to China, Wal-Mart is able to secure lower costs of inventory, which the company in turn passes on to low prices for customers.

WAL MART RETAIL UNITS IN CHINA (AS ON 28TH FEBRUARY, 2011)⁷

- Total retail units - 329
- Trust-Mart Hypermarket - 104
- Supercenter - 213
- Sam's Club - 6
- Neighborhood Market - 2
- Smart Choice - 3
- Discount Compact Hyper - 1
- Associates Wal-Mart - 66,575 Trust mart - 28,380

WAL MART MAJOR COMPETITORS IN CHINA

- Shanghai Bailian Group Co., Ltd
- Dalian Dashang Group Co., Ltd
- Shandong Sanlian Commercial Co., Ltd
- Beijing Wangfujing Department Store (Group) Co., Ltd
- Suning Appliance Chain Store Group Co., Ltd

WAL MART STRATEGIES IN CHINA

Wal-Mart has been through a lot in China and many of the lessons learned are perhaps easier to think about in retrospect, but it looks as if making the key-decisions about the China entry in real-time and under an extreme situation of uncertainty is a much more complicated task. Now, even though China has been opening to the WTO, there is still much that's unknown about the retailing future in China and with the financial crisis emanating from Wal-Mart's home market the right path for Wal-Mart is a tough call.

⁶http://www.science20.com/newswire/walmart_announces_global_responsible_sourcing_initiative_china_summit

⁷China-fact-sheet-2010

It seems that there are some major differences between Wal-Mart and Carrefour's strategy that contributed to Carrefour doing better in comparison to Wal-Mart. The main difference seems to be around the issue of adjusting to local culture. While Carrefour was mainly trying to localize and do things "the Chinese way" by encouraging local branch decision making, building local supplier contracts, stretching local rules and regulations, and using local promotion marketing schemes, Wal-Mart was more focused on doing things the American way – the way that made Wal-Mart what it is today in the American market.

This contributed to the fact that Wal-Mart has been struggling throughout many of the difficulties described above with the local customer, government and suppliers. China is considerably different than the states and yet Wal-Mart has been slow to try to adjust to that, which just might cost Wal-Mart the entire Chinese market (as it has in Germany and South Korea).

HURDLES FACED BY WAL MART IN CHINA

1. Diverse population – the Chinese people experience some huge differences in income, depending on their employment and social status, province they live in, and whether they're from an urban or a rural place. Some of the population is very poor and perhaps have different purchasing habits that pose new if not impossible challenges for retailers.
2. Too many players – the China retail market is now exploding. Foreign companies in the market enjoy relatively strong liquidity and international backing while local companies have an advantage in their in-depth knowledge of the local market, being very quick to adapt and *establish wide spread and cheap distribution systems*.
3. Local protectionism - Local governments are always following directions given by central government. There seems to be a strong local bias against foreign companies and for local and state-owned companies. State regulations against it are rarely enforced
4. Backward infrastructure - infrastructure is lacking and costly – roads are still not up to modern standards and are usually toll-based, distribution from port to destination by rail extremely slow and often require overnight storages. IT communications still far behind in most areas on both speed and connectivity.
5. Regulatory restrictions and bureaucracy– at the beginning - confining growth to 3 stores per city, and only a few cities in southern China. Government had to approve each branch. Wal-Mart abided to regulations while competitors bended those.
6. Employees – relatively unsatisfied, high turnover, low pay could not be compensated by stocks, China's mandatory labour union relatively more hostile towards foreign brands, especially Wal-Mart.
7. Highly Cultural Differences: The Chinese taste is highly different as compare to anywhere else in the world. Chinese customers like leafy vegetables & these are available in local market of china only. Wal-Mart offered in Wal-Mart in china Shenzhen, range from chicken feet, to Ma-Ling branded stewed pork ribs, & Gulong

branded pickled lettuce, which is a very different portfolio to be offered by the Wal-Mart in the United States.

8. **Different life style trend:** Chinese consumers go shopping to get out of the house, not necessarily to shop. They're more impulse driven and like on-site promotions. They're brand conscious but not loyal. They're frequent shopper of small amounts and especially appreciate freshness (alive) due to limited space at home. So, Wal-Mart's needs to go deeper in trying to understand who the consumers are and what they're looking for?

5. **Reduction in usage of plastic bags**

In 2008, the Chinese government launched efforts to curb the use of disposable plastic shopping bags. Wal-Mart supported this effort by offering customers a free reusable bag for a limited time. At the end of 2009, Wal-Mart reduced around 69% wastages of plastic bags in China.

6. **20% increase in energy efficiency**

Wal-Mart China will partner with suppliers to improve energy efficiency by 20 percent per unit of production in the top 200 factories in China from which it directly source by 2012 (2007 Baseline).

WAL MART CONTRIBUTION IN CHINA

1. **Increase in efficiency by 5% in 119 factories:**

Wal-Mart China has established around 119 factories that have demonstrated greater than 5 percent improvement in efficiency.

2. **Create zero waste in China**

Wal-Mart China reduced energy use by up to 30 percent in existing stores and opened a new store prototype that use up to 40 percent less energy.

3. **24% reduction in Energy Consumption**

Wal-Mart reduced energy consumption in existing stores of china by more than 24 percent compared to baseline stores in 2005. The high-efficiency (HE) store in Beijing is realizing energy savings of 35 percent compared to a 2005 baseline store.

4. **Participation of 280,000 farmers**

Wal-Mart has built 28 direct farm platforms in 14 provinces and municipalities with a total area of 18,666 hectares and 280,000 participating farmers in China. China expand the success of Wal-Mart China's Direct Farm Program by engaging as many as one million farmers by 2011.

AWARDS TO WAL MART IN CHINA

1. 2010 Best Corporate Social Responsibility Contribution Award of China by the Chinese Red Cross Foundation, Jinghua Commonweal Fund, and Beijing Times newspaper
2. China Women's Charity Award by All-China Women's Federation and China Women's Development Foundation
3. Best Retail Place to Work and Retail Innovation Award of 2010
4. The China Best Employer Enterprise by the International Human Resources Association
5. Leading Brand of 2010 Low-carbon China by People.com.cn.
6. The Top Charity Brand that Influences China by China Media Culture Promotion Association (CMCPA)
7. Topped the 2009 Multinational Company's Contribution to China List by the China Enterprise Federation, China Enterprise News and China CSR Research Center

8. China Top 100 Brands and Top 10 Foreign Brands at the P.R. China's 60th Anniversary by People's Net of the People's Daily and the China Newsweek
10. Ranked #1 on the "2009 Multinational Company's Contribution to China" list(China Enterprise Federation, China Enterprise News and China Corporate Social Responsibility Research Center)
11. China Green Benchmark Company 2008 – China Entrepreneur Club
12. Innovation Award – China Chain Store and Franchise Association
13. Best Employers in China 2009 by Hewitt

SWOT ANALYSIS OF WAL MART

Strengths

1. Wal-Mart is a largest corporation
2. People are key to success- suppliers.
3. Wal-Mart has grown and has experienced global expansion
4. Wal-Mart's distribution centre and logistics capabilities adding value to its entire system
5. Wal-Mart's cross-docking and effective inventory management help to sustain its Every Day Low Price Strategy.

Weaknesses:

1. Wal-Mart still to develop expertise in international marketing
2. Weak in some areas due to the huge span of control.
3. It sells products across many sectors (such as clothing, food, stationary), it may not have the flexibility of some of its more focused competitors.

Opportunities

1. Growing middle class consumers in emerging markets like China and India gives opportunity for Global expansion.
2. Growth of E-Commerce enables new business channels.
3. To take over, merge with, or form strategic alliances with other global retailers, focusing on specific emerging markets.
4. Efforts on social welfare specially in China creating better image
5. New locations and store types

Threats

1. Local and global competitors.
2. Being a global retailer means that you are exposed to political problems in the countries that you operate in.
3. Intense price competition especially in developing countries like India & China.
4. Growing trade blocks and zoning regulations hamper Wal-Mart's expansion plans

CONCLUSION

India and China have huge potential in the retail sector. Wal-Mart Stores Inc. sees great growth in China and India. International operations accounted for one-third of Wal-Mart's global sales and the proportion is expected to increase as the group focuses on larger markets in Asia.

Bharti had no presence in retail, but expected to grow in the Indian retail sector by partnering with a major global company. Wal-Mart entered in India because of larger middle class & it gets the success in India because of Low price strategies. It sourced a no of products from India include home textiles (including towels, shower curtains, bath mats, accessories, bedding sheets and kitchen linens), apparel (including woven, knitwear and leather footwear), leather

accessories, fine jewelry and house wares (including fine dining ware, home décor and tabletops).

Wal-Mart is more successful in China as compare to India. Wal-Mart is very bullish on its prospects in China because, in addition to the vast potential of its economy, the Chinese rural landscape is very similar to that of the United States, where Wal-Mart has achieved the most success. Wal-Mart actively participates in community service and charity events in China and has donated funds around RMB 65 million (USD \$9.7 million) to local communities over the past 14 years. Wal-Mart is a major factor in the economic growth in China. It increased 5% efficiency in 119 factories & created zero waste in China. Wal-Mart is included among top 100 local brands & top 10 foreign brands in China.. As a foreign operator, Wal-Mart already enjoys a reputation for high quality products in China. Frugality reigns in China, and Chinese customers are very value-oriented. So, there is great potential if Wal-Mart can successfully implement its “Everyday Low Price” strategy in China.

Thus, Wal-Mart is one of the most successful retailers in the world, is known for its low prices. Wal-Mart is the number one retailer & at the top of the Fortune 500 listing. Wal-Mart operates in many countries world-wide and is moving into new countries every year. Wal-Mart's foundation will become increasingly more important for giving things back to the community as in China. But the path in Asian countries (especially in India & China) is not easy for Wal-Mart as more people like to shop at discounters for bargains including over-the-counter drugs and eat-at-home food. Wal-Mart needs to work harder to maintain their good reputation.

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